

Sentence - Minimum Communicative Unit of Language

Khikmatova Dilrabo Pulatovna

*Lecturer of the Department of Russian Language and Literature of the Philological Faculty of
Bukhara State University*

Abstract. *The article examines single-member sentences as the most important part of syntax, in which units of all levels of language intersect and integrate. Comparative linguistics is one of the most important areas of modern linguistics. The material for the study was proverbs, riddles and texts selected from works of art by Russian and Uzbek authors.*

Key words: *sentence, syntax, semantic aspect, paradigm, language unit, sentence structure.*

The sentence is the most important part of syntax, in which units of all levels of language intersect and integrate. The history of studying syntax has a centuries-old tradition, but the question of the subject, the boundaries of this section of science continues to be relevant: there is still no unity in understanding the subject of syntax as a special section of grammar. The concept of the linguistic and speech aspects of the sentence, closely related to the understanding of intonation as a criterion for highlighting a sentence (M.N. Peterson, A.M. Peshkovsky, L.V. Shcherba, E.D. Polivanov, L.P. Yakubinsky), has received a unique development.

N.Yu.Shvedova's teaching on the paradigm of a sentence has become an integral part of modern syntactic theory, interpreted in different ways. A logically necessary consequence of substantiating the concept of a paradigm of a sentence is the identification of structural schemes of a simple sentence. Each scheme has a grammatical meaning and semantic content, characterized by a certain communicative task and one or another actual division. These dialectically related concepts serve as the basis for a multi-aspect definition of the most important syntactic unit (N.Yu.Shvedova).

The question of the nature of a sentence is one of the most difficult in syntax. It is not without reason that a sentence, occupying a central place in syntax, does not have a generally accepted definition, since it is difficult to include the entire set of features of a sentence in a definition, although, in principle, this is possible. The definitions of a sentence given by the classics of Russian linguistics tend to reflect the multi-aspect nature of a sentence or to take its semantics as a basis. Thus, the definition of a sentence given by Academician A.A. Shakhmatov mainly reflects the semantic aspect: "A sentence is a unit of speech perceived by the speaker and listener as a grammatical whole and serving for the verbal expression of a unit of thought." For a sentence, writes M.N. Peterson, two features are essential:

- 1) semantic completeness,
- 2) intonation as an expression of semantic completeness.

Based on this, the following definition of a sentence is given: "A word or combination of words representing a complete semantic and intonational unity."

Definition of a sentence: "A combination of words or a single word expressing a complete thought is called a sentence" - not incorrect, but unclear, - writes A.A. Reformatsky, - since here one unknown

(sentence) is defined through another unknown (complete thought), i.e. defined through y, and the meaning of is not revealed. In addition, there are also such sentences that express not a thought, but "feeling and desire"; such semi-definitions of a sentence as: a **sentence** is a grammatically formed unit of human speech expressing a relatively complete thought, or a reference to a reflection of reality and an expression of an attitude to this reality are not helpful. As is known, grammar deals with phenomena associated with grammatical abstraction, without having in mind specific words. Therefore, if words do not "reflect" reality or reflect it falsely, but their grammatical connections are correct, then the sentence is correct, for example: The centaur drank a round square. Obviously, when defining a sentence, one should take a different path, based on purely grammatical concepts.

V.V. Vinogradov gives the following definition of a sentence: "A sentence is a grammatically formed according to the laws of a given language, integral (i.e., indivisible further into speech units with the same basic structural features) unit of speech, which is the main means of forming, expressing and communicating thoughts. Language as a tool for communication and exchange of thoughts between all members of society uses the sentence as the main form of communication. The rules for using words in the function of sentences and the rules for combining words and phrases in a sentence are the core of the syntax of a particular language. Based on these rules, different kinds and types of sentences characteristic of a given specific language are established. A sentence expresses not only a message about reality, but also the speaker's attitude toward it. Each sentence, from a grammatical point of view, is an internal unity of its verbally expressed members, the order of their arrangement and intonation. Considering a sentence as one of the syntactic categories, the authors of the textbook "General Linguistics" write: "What does a sentence mean as a syntactic category? Information about what or whom does it express? Apparently, first of all, information about the implementation of one act of consciousness (or thinking) and the addressee of its results to the listener. That is why a sentence is a communicative unit, i.e. it does not name only some objects, phenomena, processes, features, etc. (words do this), but communicates, more or less final information, which is absolutely necessary for the implementation of an act of communication. A sentence is the minimum communicative unit of language. Its grammatical meaning is expressed by various grammatical means, which vary greatly in different languages. But one of the means is obligatory - this is the intonation of the completeness of the structure of one sentence. This intonation will have its own pattern in English, Russian, Hindustani or Swahili. But the pattern will be there, and it will be repeated, and, repeating, it will inform about the completeness of the act of consciousness and its expression." As we can see, despite the wide development of syntactic research, syntax remains one of the least studied levels, which is associated with the objective difficulties of its study: 1) the vast number of specific sentences makes it difficult to classify them; 2) the connection of syntax not only with morphology, but also with vocabulary complicates the study of any syntactic phenomenon.

The usual grammatical terms: "simple sentence" - "complex sentence", "two-part sentence" - "one-part sentence", "complete sentence" - "incomplete sentence", "declarative sentence" - "interrogative sentence" - "imperative sentence", "non-exclamatory sentence" "exclamatory sentence", etc. - stand for different syntactic categories of verbal constructions. To describe and understand each of them means to describe and understand its inherent grammatical meaning and the formal indicators expressing this meaning.

All one-member sentences of the modern Russian language P.A. Lekant divides into two main structural-grammatical types:

1. Verbal one-member sentences, which include definite-personal, indefinite-personal, generalized-personal, impersonal and infinitive sentences.

2. Nominal (substantive) one-member sentences, to which he includes nominative and genitive sentences

In the book by V.S. Yurchenko "Simple Sentence in Modern Russian" a system of types of one-member sentences is presented from the position of transformational grammar with its functional idea of the presence of primary (nuclear) and secondary (derivative) sentence structures.

The second chapter, "A Single-Part Verbal Sentence," and the third chapter, "A Single-Part Nominal Sentence," are devoted to this. According to the author of the book, in the system of types of simple sentences in modern Russian, "definite, generalized, and indefinite-personal sentences occupy an intermediate position between the main type of sentence and the impersonal verbal sentence." As for nominative sentences, they were generally derived by V.S. Yurchenko from the language system of types of simple sentences and are classified as purely speech utterances by V.S. Yurchenko.

One-member sentences as a syntactic category, along with two-member sentences, are presented in the academic experimental "Grammar of the Modern Russian Literary Language", edited by N. Yu. Shvedova. This book identifies and describes four classes of structural patterns of one-member sentences:

1. Nominal class like Night; Lots to do; People!; Not a cloud in the sky.
2. Conjugated-verb class like It's getting light; I want to talk; There's plenty to do; It's noisy outside.
3. Adverbial class like It's cold; The illness is over; We must go; There's no end in sight.
4. Infinitive class like Be silent!; He should go to the army; You can't recognize your son; You can't fit into the carriage; There's nowhere to go. Grammar of the Modern Russian Literary Language" / Edited by N. Yu. Shvedova

Up until now, we have been talking about those works on Russian syntax whose authors unconditionally recognize the one-member sentence in Russian as a syntactic reality. At the same time, individual scientists, as we have already noted, dispute and deny the very concept of a one-member sentence.

After the publication of Volume II of the Academic Grammar of the Russian Language, the theoretical work of V. G. Admoni "On the Two-Part Sentence" was published. "By its very social nature, the act of speech communication," writes V. G. Admoni in this work, "always turns out to be two-part. But this means that the linguistic unit that forms the act of speech communication, the sentence, must also be two-part in its basis, although this may not always be clearly expressed" Admoni V. G. And further: "The two-part nature of the act of speech communication is deeply connected with the two-part nature of thought-judgment. Every complete thought is two-part by its nature, created from the combination of the subject (the object or phenomenon that is defined in the thought-judgment) and the predicate (the component that defines the subject). But the two-part nature of thought means that a sentence, a linguistic unit expressing a complete thought, which must be basically two-part already by virtue of its role in the process of speech communication, receives here additional and exceptionally important stimuli in terms of its structural two-part nature. Summarizing the analysis of the grammatical structure of Russian sentences of the type Pridu; I give you my word; They say; Work; It is dawning; It is bright; It is sad, - V.G. Admoni qualifies them as two-part sentences, operating with the concept of "morphological two-part nature of a sentence", and comes to the theoretical conclusion that "two-part nature is a normal and characteristic feature of any sentence in the Russian language".

Shakhmatov's doctrine of the grammatical two-part/single-part nature of a sentence began to be revised especially intensively in the 70-80s of the last century in connection with the so-called "semantic explosion" in linguistics, including syntax. Thus, in 1969, N.D. Arutyunova attempted to return to the ideas of logical syntax of F.I. Buslaev Arutyunova N.D. Variations on the theme of a sentence // Invariant syntactic meanings and sentence structure.

In the last two decades of the last century, the traditional concept of a one-member sentence in Russian syntax was subjected to critical revision in the books of G.A. Zolotova, "An Essay on the Functional Syntax of the Russian Language" and "Communicative Aspects of Russian Syntax," in her already mentioned article "On Some Theoretical Results of the Work on the "Syntactic Dictionary of the Russian Language," published in the journal "Problems of Linguistics," as well as in a number of her other articles, in particular, "On the Possibilities of Restructuring in Teaching the Russian Language."

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